

CLINICAL-PATHOGENETIC CHARACTERISTICS AND RISK FACTORS OF ISCHEMIC STROKE IN WOMEN WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

This scientific work is devoted to the study of the clinical-pathogenetic characteristics of ischemic stroke in women against the background of metabolic syndrome and the main risk factors of its development. During the study, 250 women with metabolic syndrome between the ages of 45 and 65 were monitored. The research methodology included anamnesis collection, clinical and laboratory examinations, as well as assessment of blood glucose and lipid spectrum. The results showed that women with metabolic syndrome have a significantly higher risk of developing ischemic stroke, especially in the presence of arterial hypertension, impaired glucose tolerance, high triglyceride levels and low LPVP-cholesterol values. Thus, early diagnosis and management of metabolic syndrome are important in reducing the risk of developing ischemic stroke in women. The work emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach, which includes lifestyle correction, diet and drug treatment, in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases.

Key words: ischemic stroke, metabolic syndrome, women, risk factors, arterial hypertension, carbohydrate metabolism disorder, dyslipidemia, prevention, clinical-pathogenetic characteristics

ENTER

Ischemic stroke is a serious disease caused by sudden disruption of cerebral circulation, which is one of the main causes of disability and death globally. Preventing and treating ischemic stroke is important for health care systems, as this disease has a negative impact on a person's quality of life.

Metabolic syndrome is a complex of diseases that includes factors such as high blood pressure, excess weight, high blood sugar and fat content, which increases the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases. Individuals with metabolic syndrome may have a higher risk of developing ischemic stroke, which requires the study of this condition and the development of effective preventive measures against it.

In women, the impact of metabolic syndrome on ischemic stroke may be different than in men, which is related to hormonal differences, lifestyle and biological characteristics. Therefore, in-depth study of the mechanisms of development of ischemic stroke and its clinical-pathogenetic characteristics in women against the background of metabolic syndrome, as well as the identification of risk factors, is an urgent task today.

The main goal of this study is to find ways to prevent and effectively treat this disease by studying the clinical-pathogenetic characteristics and risk factors of ischemic stroke in women against the background of metabolic syndrome.

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to determine the clinical-pathogenetic characteristics of ischemic stroke observed in women against the background of metabolic syndrome and to evaluate the main risk factors of its development.

Material and methods

The study was conducted among 250 women with metabolic syndrome aged 45 to 65 years. Methods such as anamnesis collection, clinical and laboratory examinations, including a detailed analysis of blood glucose and lipid profile, arterial pressure measurement were used for data collection.

Results

The results of the study showed that among women with metabolic syndrome, the risk of developing ischemic stroke is relatively high, especially under the influence of factors such as arterial hypertension, impaired glucose tolerance, high triglyceride levels and low LPVP-cholesterol indicators.

Summary

There are certain clinical and pathogenetic features in the development of ischemic stroke associated with metabolic syndrome, which should be taken into account when developing strategies for the prevention and treatment of the disease in women. The main results of the study emphasize the need for early diagnosis and effective management of metabolic syndrome in women, as well as the need for comprehensive approaches to prevent cardiovascular diseases.